

Using *OpenSimRoot* to simulate barley root growth to identify stress-resilient traits

Problem

Barley is an important crop that is known for its stress-tolerance. Its root system comprises distinct classes, including seminal and nodal roots, crucial for resource uptake. Studying certain traits systematically is sometimes not possible under field conditions. Also, investigating roots in the field is difficult as experiments are costly, time-consuming, and the results are affected by environmental conditions.

Solution

The growth of barley root systems is simulated with *OpenSimRoot*, a software for functional-structural plant modelling in 3D soil, to investigate how root traits affect plant performance under stress.

Benefits

This approach allows for the systematic testing of individual and combined traits while reducing time and cost. The results can guide breeding efforts towards barley ideotypes that are better adapted to future stress.

Practical application

This model is publicly available and can be directly applied by following the installation and simulation instructions provided below.

Set-up *OpenSimRoot*.

Download *OpenSimRoot* in a new folder. Open a terminal (e.g., PowerShell in Windows), create a directory, and download the software:

```
PS C:\Users\user.name> mkdir OSR_example
```

```
PS C:\Users\user.name> cd OSR_example
```

```
PS C:\Users\user.name\OSR_example> wget.exe http://rootmodels.gitlab.io/OpenSimRoot/executables/OpenSimRoot_Win_x64.exe
```

Download the test input files and unzip:

```
PS C:\Users\user.name\OSR_example> wget.exe http://rootmodels.gitlab.io/OpenSimRoot/inputfiles/inputfiles_osr.zip
```

```
PS C:\Users\user.name\OSR_example> Expand-Archive .\inputfiles_osr.zip
```

Run a barley simulation.

```
PS C:\Users\user.name\OSR_example> .\OpenSimRoot_Win_x64.exe .\inputfiles_osr\OpenSimRoot\InputFiles\runBarley.xml
```

View data

OpenSimRoot will create a file "tabled_output.xls" and the 3D root system and, if enabled, the soil as vtu/pvd files that can be viewed in Paraview (www.paraview.org).

Applicability box

Theme: Root modelling toolbox

Keywords: Barley, root growth, functional-structural plant model (FSPM), root system architecture (RSA), simulation

Context: Simulations across regions and environments

Required time:

Installation: within minutes

Simulation: from minutes to hours

Equipment: Computer with *OpenSimRoot* and Paraview for visualisation

Software/hardware for data acquisition/analysis, e.g., RhizoVision Explorer or WinRhizo

Example: Analyse the impact of traits

Set up the input files for studying the trait (here lateral root diameter): The input file “runBarley.xml” is specific to a barley genotype and defines root classes, including values for elongation and branching. Change the diameter of lateral roots in the xml file:

```
<SimulaDirective path="lateral">
...
  <SimulaConstant name="diameter" unit="cm"> 0.01 </SimulaConstant>
...
</SimulaDirective>
```


Figure 1: Root architecture and water uptake patterns, and associated shoot growth in barley

(A) 3D barley root architectures after 70 days of growth with thin (left) and thick (right) lateral roots providing a spatial view of how water uptake varies across root segments. Colours show water uptake, ranging from light blue (water loss) to orange (water uptake). The depicted water loss from the roots appeared at later timepoints into dry soil.

(B) Shoot dry weight and (C) leaf area over 70 days in barley with thin (0.01 cm, blue) and thick (0.05 cm, orange) lateral root diameters, linking root water uptake to aboveground growth performance.

Further information

- Root2Res. (2025) Using OpenSimRoot to model faba bean root growth. <https://zenodo.org/records/17738382>
- Root2Res. (2025) Using OpenSimRoot to model sweet potato root growth. <https://zenodo.org/records/17738430>
- Postma, J.A., Kuppe, C., Owen, M.R., Mellor, N., Griffiths, M., Bennett, M.J., Lynch, J.P. and Watt, M. (2017), OpenSimRoot: widening the scope and application of root architectural models. *New Phytol*, 215: 1274-1286. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.14641>
- Postma J.A. & Black K. (2020) CH02 - Advances in root architectural modeling during the last decade. In *Understanding and improving crop root function. Advances in modelling plant root systems*, p. 34. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, UK. <http://dx.doi.org/10.19103/AS.2020.0075.02>
- Schäfer, E.D., Owen, M.R., Postma, J.A., Kuppe, C., Black, C.K., Lynch, J.P. (2022). Simulating Crop Root Systems Using OpenSimRoot. In: Lucas, M. (eds) *Plant Systems Biology. Methods in Molecular Biology*, vol 2395. Humana, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-1816-5_15
- OpenSimRoot weblink: <https://rootmodels.gitlab.io/>

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

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Root2Resilience: The project is running from September 2022 to August 2027. The overall goal of Root2Resilience – Root phenotyping and genetic improvement for rotational crops resilient to environmental change – is to develop root phenotyping, genetic and modelling tools and use them to define and test innovative genotype ideotypes able to enhance the tolerance to abiotic stress and carbon sequestration in soils.

Project website: root2res.eu

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